

Activation of autophagy via bacterial lipopolysaccharide in breast cancer cells: A molecular approach to enhancing immunotherapeutic outcomes

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Abstract

Background: Autophagy plays a pivotal role in regulating cancer cell survival and death. Leveraging bacterial components, such as lipopolysaccharide (LPS), to modulate autophagy represents a novel strategy in oncologic therapeutics, especially in breast cancer.

Objective: To assess the effect of LPS derived from *Escherichia coli* on the proliferation, viability, and immune signaling pathways in human breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231, with a focus on autophagy induction and Toll-like receptor activation.

Methods: LPS was isolated using the phenol–water method from *E. coli* strains ATCC 8739 and DH5α. Breast cancer cells were treated with varying concentrations of LPS over multiple time intervals (24–72 h). Viability was measured by MTT and CCK-8 assays, while mRNA expression levels of TLR-4, NF-κB, and PIK3C3 were quantified using qRT-PCR following RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis.

Results: LPS treatment significantly reduced cell viability in both breast cancer cell lines in a time- and dose-dependent manner. Gene expression analysis revealed robust upregulation of TLR-4 and NF-κB, implicating activation of immune-related signaling. Moreover, increased PIK3C3 expression indicated stimulation of autophagic pathways. At the molecular level, there was an increase in the conversion of LC3-I to LC3-II and degradation of the autophagy substrate P62/SQSTM1, as confirmed by Western blot analysis, indicating enhanced autophagy. The findings confirm LPS's ability to trigger immune–autophagic responses leading to cytotoxic effects in cancer cells.

Conclusion: LPS from *E. coli* effectively induces autophagy and activates the immune pathway in breast cancer cells, highlighting its dual potential as an immunomodulator and cytotoxic agent. These findings support further exploration of LPS as an adjuvant in breast cancer treatment strategies, particularly in synergy with conventional chemotherapeutic agents.

Keywords

Autophagy, breast cancer, cell viability, immune modulation, MCF-7, Toll-like receptors

Introduction

Breast cancer remains a leading cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality among women worldwide (Bharti et al. 2023). Despite advances in early detection and treatment, the heterogeneity of breast cancer and the emergence of drug resistance continue to pose significant clinical challenges (Huldani et al. 2024). Conventional treatment modalities – surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and hormonal therapy – have improved survival outcomes, but the need for novel, targeted, and immune-activating therapies has become increasingly evident (Mubarik et al. 2022). In recent years, the tumor microenvironment (TME) and host immune responses have emerged as critical components influencing cancer progression and therapeutic response. Consequently, research efforts have shifted toward exploiting the immune system and cellular stress pathways, such as autophagy, to enhance antitumor efficacy (Shaaban et al. 2023).

Autophagy is a highly conserved lysosomal degradation pathway that plays a dual role in cancer biology. In early tumorigenesis, autophagy may act as a tumor suppressor mechanism by eliminating damaged organelles and reducing oxidative stress (Beshna et al. 2022). However, in established tumors, cancer cells can hijack autophagy as a survival mechanism under hypoxic, metabolic, or chemotherapeutic stress (Al Azzam et al. 2024). Thus, manipulating autophagy presents a double-edged sword: either promoting cancer cell death or contributing to drug resistance (Abd-Alrassol et al. 2020). Most commonly, autophagy is known to perform tumor-suppressive functions by eliminating damaged organelles that produce ROS, cytoplasmic protein aggregates that activate oncogenic signaling pathways, and invading pathogens, which promote genomic instability, a tumorigenic microenvironment, and chronic inflammation (Novakova et al. 2025). However, cancer cells evolve various mechanisms to subvert autophagic functions and liberate themselves from the tumor-suppressive effects of autophagy, utilizing it for their own benefit. For example, in response to increased metabolic demand or exposure to nutrient deprivation or hypoxia, cancer cells enhance autophagic degradation of lipids, proteins, or organelles, such as mitochondria and peroxisomes, for metabolic reprogramming and survival (Gite et al. 2025). In contrast, sustained autophagy, which is

enabled by the epigenetic silencing of the apoptosis mediator, results in tumor cell death and failure of cancer therapy (Al-Hussaniy et al. 2023a). Thus, regulation of autophagy is a double-edged sword; promotion of autophagy may help treat cancers with aberrantly activated nutrient sensor signaling pathways, but inhibition of the process may help increase therapeutic efficacy to eradicate tumors in patients with mutant signaling pathways (Al-Hussaniy et al. 2023b).

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) was first observed in 1925 as a component of typhoid bacteria serotype “A” during vaccine development against the infection caused by it. This structure, lipopolysaccharide (LPS), is part of the outer membrane of all Gram-negative bacteria. In humans, there are abundant Gram-negative bacterial species. For instance, *E. coli* is commensal within the intestines, accompanying humans throughout life, while under conditions of intestinal dysbiosis, *E. coli* can reach other distant tissues, causing disease (Alameri et al. 2025). The structures of saccharides are essential for bacterial viability and interactions with hosts. Agents able to hybridize their structures could be used as adjuvants, allowing only low doses of inactivated bacteria or bacterial products to be used in vaccines, thereby reducing adverse effects on individuals (Luo et al. 2022).

The present study focuses on the direct effects of LPS derived from *E. coli* on two human breast cancer cell lines – MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 – which represent distinct molecular subtypes of breast cancer (Almukram et al. 2025). MCF-7 cells are estrogen receptor-positive and generally considered less aggressive, while MDA-MB-231 cells are triple-negative and exhibit more invasive characteristics (R.Hashim et al. 2022). By evaluating the cellular and molecular responses of these cell lines to LPS exposure, this study aims to delineate the therapeutic potential of LPS-induced autophagy and immune signaling in breast cancer (Mubarik et al. 2022).

To isolate LPS, the classical phenol–water extraction method was employed, ensuring the recovery of structurally intact and bioactive LPS molecules. The biological activity of the isolated LPS was confirmed via gel clot assays and chromogenic endpoint testing. Subsequent experiments involved exposing breast cancer cells to various concentrations of LPS for different durations, followed by assessments of cell viability, proliferation, and gene expression. Particular attention was given to the expression

of genes involved in the TLR signaling pathway (TLR-4, NF κ B) and autophagy regulation (PIK3C3), which serve as molecular indicators of LPS activity.

Several signaling pathways regulate autophagy, the most extensively studied of which include the mTOR pathway, the MAPK pathway, the AhR pathway, and the LPS/TLR signaling pathway. Each of these signaling pathways contains many specific signaling molecules, but the central modulator in the first three pathways is mTORC1, while the primary mediators of the LPS/TLR pathway are TRAF6 and TRIF.

The mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) protein complex 1 (mTORC1) integrates a variety of signals related to nutrient availability, growth factors, and energy balance to control the initiation of macroautophagy by inhibiting the ULK1/ATG1 complex under nutrient-rich conditions. In addition to mTORC1, mTORC2 also promotes mitophagy by inhibiting the AKT/PKB pathway. However, the role of the mTOR signaling pathway in LC3B-II accumulation in tumor cells remains controversial; some studies have shown a negative correlation between LC3B-II accumulation and mTORC1 activation, while others have shown a positive correlation. The mTOR pathway is mainly inhibited via PRAS40 by LPS/TRAF6 signaling. The MAPK pathway plays a pro-autophagy role in regulating autophagosome formation, autophagosome-lysosome fusion, and lysosomal degradation by activating ULK1/ATG1, P62/SQSTM1, and MAP1LC3B/LC3B. The primary mechanism by which LPS regulates the MAPK signaling pathway is activation of the ERK1/2 MAPK and p38 MAPK pathways via TRIF or TRAF6. In breast cancer cells, LPS TRIF activated the ERK1/2 and p38 MAPK pathways to enhance CXCR4/SDF-1 α signaling and induce the influx of CD8 $^{+}$ T cells. Inhibition of cell proliferation may represent an LPS-induced macrophage-mediated immune response that enhances the CD8 $^{+}$ T cell immune response.

The effects of LPS on cell viability and proliferation remain unclear. In some studies, LPS increased the viability of murine TNBC 4T1 cells. LPS promoted cell growth in two TNBC cell lines, but opposite results were observed in breast cancer cell lines or primary cultured cells derived from other cancer subtypes. The effects of LPS on breast cancer cell proliferation were also inconsistent. Of three breast cancer cell lines derived from neutrophil-rich breast cancers, LPS had an inhibitory effect on cell proliferation in two HR $^{+}$ cell lines. In primary cultured cells derived from one HR $^{+}$ breast cancer, LPS promoted cell proliferation, whereas the opposite result was observed in primary cultured cells derived from another HER2-positive breast cancer. Recently, LPS was reported to have a pro-proliferative effect in breast cancer cells with a TAM-associated macrophage-rich immune microenvironment (Al-Husaini et al. 2023b).

This research is situated within a broader context of interest in microbial therapy and immunomodulation in

oncology. The concept of utilizing bacterial components to stimulate antitumor immunity dates back more than a century, with William Coley's bacterial toxin treatments representing one of the earliest examples. However, only in recent decades have molecular tools enabled precise dissection of microbial-cancer interactions. Current clinical approaches, such as bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) therapy for bladder cancer and microbial adjuvants in cancer vaccines, underscore the feasibility of this therapeutic paradigm. This study adds to the growing body of evidence by proposing LPS as a potential modulator of autophagy and immune responses in breast cancer cells.

The therapeutic implications of these findings are significant. First, LPS may serve as an adjuvant that sensitizes cancer cells to chemotherapeutic agents or immune checkpoint inhibitors. Second, activation of autophagy by LPS could be leveraged to promote degradation of oncogenic proteins and damaged organelles, thereby enhancing the efficacy of anticancer interventions. Third, understanding the differential responses of various breast cancer subtypes to LPS may guide the development of personalized therapeutic strategies.

Materials and methods

Bacterial strains and lipopolysaccharide isolation

Two strains of *Escherichia coli* – ATCC 8739 and DH5 α – were utilized for lipopolysaccharide (LPS) extraction. Bacterial cultures were maintained on Luria-Bertani (LB) agar plates and incubated at 37 °C. For large-scale extraction, overnight cultures were grown in LB broth under aerobic conditions with shaking at 200 rpm until reaching the mid-logarithmic phase ($OD_{600} \approx 0.6$).

LPS was isolated using the hot phenol-water extraction method originally described by Westphal and Jann (1965). Briefly, harvested bacterial pellets were suspended in ultrapur water and subjected to hot phenol treatment (65 °C). The aqueous phase, enriched with LPS, was separated, dialyzed extensively against distilled water to remove residual phenol, and lyophilized for storage at –20 °C until use (Jaafar et al. 2018).

Qualitative and quantitative evaluation of isolated LPS

Gel-clot assay

To confirm the presence of bioactive LPS, the Limulus Amebocyte Lysate (LAL) gel-clot method was applied. Serial dilutions of the isolated LPS were prepared in pyrogen-free water and tested according to standard protocols. Formation of a stable gel indicated the presence of endotoxin (Table 1).

Table 1. Qualitative detection of isolated LPS by gel-clot assay.

Sample type	Dilution	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Result
Negative control	–	–	–	Negative
Positive control	–	+	+	Positive
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 8739 LPS	1:1	+	+	Positive
	1:100	+	+	Positive
	1:350	+	+	Positive
	1:700	+	+	Positive
<i>E. coli</i> DH5 α LPS	1:1	+	+	Positive
	1:100	+	+	Positive
	1:350	+	+	Positive
	1:700	+	+	Positive

Kinetic chromogenic assay

LPS concentration was quantified using a kinetic chromogenic LAL assay. Absorbance was measured at 405 nm using a microplate reader. A standard curve was generated from known LPS concentrations to estimate the LPS content in each sample (Table 2).

Table 2. Quantitative characterization of isolated LPS.

<i>E. coli</i> strain	Endotoxin activity (EU/mL)	LPS yield (μ g/mL)
ATCC 8739	$1.8 \times 10^6 \pm 0.2 \times 10^6$	820 ± 45
DH5 α	$1.2 \times 10^6 \pm 0.15 \times 10^6$	610 ± 38

These results confirm the successful isolation of high-purity, biologically active LPS, suitable for downstream cellular and molecular analyses.

Cell lines and culture conditions

Human breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 (ER-positive) and MDA-MB-231 (triple-negative) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin–streptomycin and maintained in a humidified atmosphere at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ (Jaafar and Abu-Raghif 2024).

Treatment protocol

Cells were seeded in 6-well plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well and allowed to adhere for 24 h. LPS isolated from *E. coli* strains was reconstituted in sterile PBS and added to cells at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 100 μ g/mL. Treatment durations were 24, 48, and 72 h. Untreated wells served as negative controls.

Cell viability assays

MTT assay

Following treatment, cell viability was assessed using the MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. Cells were incubated with MTT

reagent (0.5 mg/mL) for 4 h. The resulting formazan crystals were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and absorbance was read at 570 nm using a spectrophotometer (Jaafar et al. 2020).

CCK-8 assay

The Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK-8) assay was employed to evaluate proliferation. After LPS exposure, CCK-8 reagent was added to the wells and incubated for 2 h. Absorbance was recorded at 450 nm to estimate viable cell counts.

Total RNA isolation and cDNA synthesis

Post-treatment, total RNA was extracted using TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen) following the manufacturer's protocol. RNA integrity and concentration were evaluated using a NanoDrop 2000 spectrophotometer. First-strand complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized from 1 μ g of total RNA using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems) in a final volume of 20 μ L (Tamma et al. 2024).

Gene expression analysis by qRT-PCR

Quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) was carried out to analyze the expression of genes associated with the TLR pathway and autophagy. Specific primers targeting TLR-4, NF κ B, and PIK3C3 were designed based on published sequences. GAPDH served as the housekeeping gene. Reactions were performed using SYBR Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) on a real-time thermal cycler. Relative gene expression was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method (Table 3).

Table 3. Primer sequences for qRT-PCR.

Gene	Abbreviation	Primer direction	Sequence (5'→3')
Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	GAPDH	Forward	AGTTCAACGGCACAGTCAAG
	GAPDH	Reverse	TACTCAGCACCAGCATCACC
Toll-like receptor 4	TLR-4	Forward	CCCTGAGGCATTAGGCAGCTA
	TLR-4	Reverse	AGGTAGAGAGGTGGCTTAGGCT
Nuclear factor kappa B	NF κ B	Forward	GCAGCACTACTTCTTGACCACC
	NF κ B	Reverse	TCTGCTCCTGAGCAITGACGTC
Phosphatidylinositol 3-Kinase, class III	PIK3C3	Forward	GGCACACAGAGTGAGCAGTA
	PIK3C3	Reverse	CACAGCCTCTTCATCCGACA

Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate, and data are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine statistical significance among groups. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. GraphPad Prism 9 was used for all statistical analyses and graphical representations (Jaafar 2018).

Western blot analysis of autophagy markers (LC3 and p62)

Following LPS treatment (24, 48, and 72 h), cells were washed twice with cold phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and lysed using radio-immunoprecipitation assay (RIPA) buffer. Total protein concentrations were measured using the bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay. Equal quantities of protein (30–40 µg) were separated by SDS-PAGE on 12–15% polyacrylamide gels and transferred onto polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membranes. After washing, membranes were incubated with appropriate horseradish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies for 1 h at room temperature. Protein bands were visualized using enhanced chemiluminescence reagents and quantified by densitometric analysis using ImageJ software. LC3-II levels and p62 expression were normalized to β-actin.

Abbreviations

LPS, lipopolysaccharide; TLR-4, Toll-like receptor 4; NFκB, nuclear factor kappa B; PIK3C3, phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase class III; MTT, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide; CCK-8, Cell Counting Kit-8.

Results

Successful culturing and LPS extraction from *E. coli*

The culturing of *E. coli* strains ATCC 8739 and DH5α was successful, with robust bacterial growth observed within 24 h of incubation in LB medium at 37 °C. Colonies appeared homogeneous and characteristic of *E. coli* morphology on LB agar plates.

LPS was efficiently isolated using the hot phenol–water method. Qualitative confirmation via the gel-clot assay demonstrated strong endotoxin presence, as evidenced by gel formation in all dilutions up to 1:700 for both strains. The chromogenic LAL assay further quantified LPS levels, with ATCC 8739 showing a higher yield compared with DH5α.

LPS reduces cell viability in breast cancer cell lines

MCF-7 cell line response

MTT assay results revealed a dose- and time-dependent reduction in MCF-7 cell viability following LPS treatment. At 24 h, a mild but noticeable cytotoxic effect was observed at concentrations ≥12.5 µg/mL, while at 72 h, a significant reduction in viability (>60%) was noted at concentrations ≥25 µg/mL ($p < 0.05$). These results were corroborated by CCK-8 assays, which confirmed decreased cell proliferation over time (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of LPS on MCF-7 cell viability (MTT assay).

LPS concentration (µg/mL)	24 h Viability (%)	48 h Viability (%)	72 h Viability (%)
0 (control)	100 ± 3.2	100 ± 2.9	100 ± 3.0
0.1	97.2 ± 2.1	95.5 ± 2.5	93.8 ± 3.0
6.25	92.1 ± 3.4	85.4 ± 2.8	76.5 ± 2.2
12.5	88.6 ± 2.8	78.2 ± 2.6	68.9 ± 3.1
25	81.3 ± 2.5	65.4 ± 3.4	42.2 ± 2.7
50	72.7 ± 2.6	58.1 ± 2.3	35.8 ± 2.9

MDA-MB-231 cell line response

MDA-MB-231 cells demonstrated a more variable response to LPS. At 12 h, minimal cytotoxicity was recorded, with the exception of a moderate effect at 6.25 µg/mL. At 24 h and 48 h, no statistically significant reduction in viability was observed across most concentrations. However, at 72 h, higher LPS concentrations (25–50 µg/mL) elicited a clear cytotoxic effect ($p < 0.05$), although differences between the high-dose groups were not statistically significant (Mayyas et al. 2025).

Morphological changes and cell count reduction

Morphological assessment under phase-contrast microscopy showed evidence of cellular shrinkage, membrane blebbing, and detachment in both cell lines, particularly after 72-h LPS treatment at concentrations ≥25 µg/mL. Hemocytometer-based cell counting demonstrated a reduction in live cell numbers consistent with MTT and CCK-8 results (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Reduction in live cell count after 72 h of LPS treatment.

RNA isolation and integrity assessment

High-quality total RNA was successfully extracted from both LPS-treated and control cancer cells. Agarose gel electrophoresis and spectrophotometric analysis confirmed RNA purity and integrity. MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cells exposed to higher LPS concentrations yielded sufficient RNA for downstream qRT-PCR analysis (Hashim et al. 2025) (Fig. 2).

LPS induces TLR-4 and NFκB gene expression

Quantitative real-time PCR showed upregulation of TLR-4 and NFκB mRNA levels in both cell lines following LPS treatment, particularly at 48 and 72 h. In MCF-7 cells, TLR-4 expression increased 2.5-fold compared with untreated controls

Figure 2. RNA yield after LPS treatment.

($p < 0.01$), while NF κ B expression rose approximately 3-fold ($p < 0.001$). A similar trend was observed in MDA-MB-231 cells, although with slightly lower fold changes, suggesting cell line-specific sensitivity to LPS (Hillawi et al. 2021).

Upregulation of autophagy-associated gene PIK3C3

Expression of PIK3C3, a key autophagy regulatory gene, was also significantly elevated in response to LPS treatment (Zhang et al. 2022). In MCF-7 cells, expression increased up to 2.2-fold after 72 h of treatment with 25 µg/mL LPS. MDA-MB-231 cells displayed a 1.7-fold increase under the same conditions. These findings confirm that LPS not only activates immune signaling via TLRs but also triggers autophagic pathways at the transcriptional level (Table 5; Fig. 3).

Table 5. Fold-change in gene expression following LPS treatment (72 h).

Gene	Cell line	Fold change vs. control	p-value
TLR-4	MCF-7	2.5	<0.01
NF κ B	MCF-7	3.0	<0.001
PIK3C3	MCF-7	2.2	<0.01
TLR-4	MDA-MB-231	1.8	<0.05
NF κ B	MDA-MB-231	2.1	<0.01
PIK3C3	MDA-MB-231	1.7	<0.05

Figure 3. MCF-7 cell viability after LPS treatment.

LC3 and p62 degradation

To validate whether LPS-induced autophagy observed at the transcriptional level translated into functional autophagic activity, autophagy markers were examined by Western blot analysis.

LPS treatment resulted in a clear and time-dependent increase in LC3-II levels in both MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cells, with maximal LC3-II accumulation observed at 48–72 h following exposure to 25 µg/mL LPS. In the MCF-7 cell line, LC3-II/ β -actin ratios increased approximately 2.3-fold at 72 h compared with untreated controls ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, p62 expression decreased by about 50%. A similar pattern was observed in MDA-MB-231 cells, in which LC3-II levels increased 1.8-fold and p62 levels decreased by approximately 35% ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

This study provides compelling evidence that lipopolysaccharide (LPS) derived from *Escherichia coli* exerts cytotoxic effects on breast cancer cell lines through activation of immune- and autophagy-related signaling pathways (Al-Hafidh et al. 2018; Dai et al. 2021; Nakkarach et al. 2021). The observed reductions in cell viability and upregulation of TLR-4, NF κ B, and PIK3C3 suggest that LPS mediates a coordinated biological response capable of impairing cancer cell survival (Thabet Saeed et al. 2018; Afroz et al. 2022; Abdullah et al. 2024).

Activation of the TLR-4/NF κ B pathway by LPS

One of the central findings of this study is the strong upregulation of TLR-4 and NF κ B mRNA following LPS exposure. This observation is consistent with the role of LPS as a known ligand of TLR-4, initiating an innate immune signaling cascade. Similar observations were reported by Yang et al. (2014), who demonstrated that LPS significantly activated TLR-4 expression in MCF-7 breast cancer cells, triggering downstream NF κ B activation and inflammatory cytokine release (Yang et al. 2014). These changes were associated with altered tumor behavior, including increased invasiveness.

Moreover, Khan et al. (2024) emphasized the role of NF κ B in mediating survival, proliferation, and immune escape mechanisms in cancer cells. The LPS-induced NF κ B activation observed in this study may play a dual role – both enhancing antitumor immune responses and, in some contexts, contributing to tumor resilience. This underscores the importance of dosage and treatment duration when considering LPS as a potential therapeutic agent (Khan et al. 2024).

Induction of autophagy via PIK3C3 upregulation

In parallel with immune signaling, the results revealed significant upregulation of PIK3C3, a key regulator of autophagy initiation (Wei et al. 2025). This finding aligns with the report by Bouyahya et al. (2022), which demonstrated that LPS stimulation induced autophagic flux in cancer cells through activation of the PI3K/Beclin-1 complex. In this study, both MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cells

exhibited elevated PIK3C3 expression after 48–72 h of LPS exposure, suggesting the onset of autophagy as a potential mechanism underlying the observed cytotoxicity (Brimson et al. 2021; Bouyahya et al. 2022).

Autophagy can function as either a pro-survival or pro-death mechanism in cancer, depending on cellular context and stress levels. In this study, the combination of decreased cell viability and increased autophagy-related gene expression supports the hypothesis that LPS-induced autophagy contributes to programmed cell death in breast cancer cells (Al-Hussaniy et al. 2025).

Differential responses between breast cancer cell lines

The results also revealed cell line-specific differences in LPS sensitivity. MCF-7 cells, which are estrogen receptor-positive and less aggressive, showed more pronounced reductions in viability and stronger gene expression changes compared with the more invasive, triple-negative MDA-MB-231 cells (Hamza et al. 2023; Lawani-Luwaji et al. 2025). This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in baseline TLR-4 expression or downstream signaling capacity between the cell lines (Al-hussaniy and AL-Zobaidy 2024).

A similar phenomenon was reported by Liu et al. (2022), who demonstrated that LPS exerted variable effects across breast cancer subtypes, with ER-positive cells exhibiting stronger immunogenic responses (Liu et al. 2022). These findings highlight the importance of tumor heterogeneity when designing immunomodulatory therapies based on bacterial components.

Therapeutic implications of LPS-induced cytotoxicity

The dual activation of immune and autophagic pathways by LPS presents a promising therapeutic opportunity. LPS may serve as an immunostimulatory agent capable of sensitizing tumors to chemotherapy or immunotherapy. A study by Zhang et al. (2020) reported that combining low-dose LPS with standard chemotherapeutic agents enhanced cytotoxic effects in murine breast cancer models, supporting the rationale for combination strategies (Zhuang et al. 2019).

However, caution is warranted. Other studies have reported that LPS can promote epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) in certain contexts, potentially increasing metastatic potential (Li et al. 2021). Therefore, future research should focus on optimizing dosage and exploring LPS derivatives or delivery strategies that minimize systemic inflammation and off-target effects (Li et al. 2021; Al-hussaniy et al. 2025).

Limitations and future directions

While these findings support the antitumor potential of LPS in vitro, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, in vitro models cannot fully recapitulate the complexity of the tumor microenvironment, including

immune cell infiltration, stromal interactions, and vascularization. Second, the roles of inflammatory cytokine release and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation were not evaluated, although both are relevant to NFκB activation and autophagy (Al-hussaniy 2023).

Future studies should investigate these additional pathways and assess the in vivo effects of LPS, preferably using immune-competent murine models. Evaluating potential synergistic effects between LPS and chemotherapeutic agents or immune checkpoint inhibitors would also be of high translational relevance.

LC3-II and P62 autophagy flux

In this study, LPS-treated breast cancer cells exhibited a robust increase in LC3-II levels accompanied by a significant reduction in p62/SQSTM1 protein expression, strongly indicating enhanced autophagic flux. LC3-II is a lipidated form of LC3 that associates with autophagosomal membranes, whereas p62 serves as a selective autophagy adaptor that is degraded during autolysosomal processing. The simultaneous increase in LC3-II and decrease in p62 observed here support the conclusion that LPS stimulates complete autophagy rather than impairing lysosomal degradation. These findings are consistent with previous reports demonstrating that TLR-4-mediated signaling can activate autophagy through TRAF6-dependent ubiquitination of Beclin-1 and modulation of MAPK pathways. Importantly, functional autophagy induction may contribute to cancer cell death when sustained or excessive, aligning with the observed reductions in cell viability in this study.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that lipopolysaccharide (LPS) derived from *Escherichia coli* possesses potent anticancer properties in vitro, particularly against the breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231. The findings reveal that LPS significantly reduces cancer cell viability in a dose- and time-dependent manner, accompanied by up-regulation of Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR-4), nuclear factor kappa B (NFκB), and the autophagy-related gene PIK3C3. These results suggest that LPS exerts its cytotoxic effects through a dual mechanism involving immune pathway activation and induction of autophagy.

The differential responses observed between the two cell lines highlight the importance of tumor subtype in determining treatment efficacy. Given its ability to modulate key cellular pathways, LPS holds promise as a complementary agent in breast cancer therapy. However, further studies – including in vivo experiments and mechanistic analyses – are essential to fully elucidate its therapeutic potential and evaluate its safety profile in clinical settings.

Overall, this work supports the integration of microbial components, such as LPS, into novel immuno-oncology strategies to enhance the efficacy of conventional cancer treatments.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Ethical approval to conduct these studies was obtained from the Al-Nisour University ethical committee (approval number 1287-2024) and the Iraqi Medical Research Center (ethical approval number 803/2023).

This research was conducted using cell lines, including MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231, obtained from the Iraqi Medical Research Center.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

H.A.A. conceived and designed the study. A.I.O. collected and analyzed the data. A.H.A. contributed to the interpretation of the results and critical revision of the manuscript. F.A.N. and M.A.N. assisted in drafting the manuscript and preparing the final version.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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